

IMPORTANT FACTS ABOUT VARICOSE

VEINS:

It is very easy to spot varicose veins. The veins are usually enlarged and twisted. The veins usually appear on the legs. Some people seem more prone to varicose veins. Research shows that the cause is often genetic which means that there is a long history of the disease in the family. Researchers further state that a family genetic weakness in the veins causes the veins to become overloaded with blood thus causing the gnarled blue veins. In such a case, you need **vein treatment**.

Statistics show that men and women are bothered by this often painful condition although the vast majority of sufferers are women. Varicose veins usually erupt when there is a problem with blood flow. The blood flowing is not proper through the veins. The blood becomes trapped on its journey back through the lower extremities and to the heart. The blood flow is trapped in that area which causes the veins to bulge and become gnarled. The appearance is usually quite upsetting and embarrassing to the individual who suffers from the condition.

Actually, there is no reason to just accept the embarrassing condition. There are several methods to cope and end the suffering. If you want to eliminate the unsightly veins, consult a [vein specialist near me North Shore](#) for **varicose vein treatment**.

Let's take a look at a few of the **natural ways** to treat varicose veins.

- One way to cope and control the problem is to exercise. Any exercise that uses leg power is great. Exercise keeps the blood flowing through the veins and back to the heart, thus preventing the condition. If it is not working, you can get **varicose vein treatment li**.
- Overweight people are also more prone to developing the condition. Consequently, it is important to keep the weight under control to stop the development of varicose veins.

- People who have jobs where they are on their feet all day long have a tendency to develop varicose veins. The reason is that the blood has difficulty flowing back to the heart because of the gravitational pull downward. Gravity slows the blood flow in the legs and causes the condition. That is why it is vitally important to sit down and take a break from standing to rest the legs. Otherwise, get **varicose vein treatment near me li**.

Let's move onto a more permanent **vein treatments South Shore**:

There are a variety of laser surgeries that can be used to minimize the appearance of smaller varicose veins or spider veins Such as:

- Professionals use intense pulsed light (IPL) treatment that functions on the transmission of a certain range of frequency of light into the veins. This process arouses the origin of collagen that gradually makes the veins vanish eventually. No incisions are made while performing this **vein treatment on Hamptons**.
- Another method for varicose treatment is sclerotherapy. During this method, a **vein specialist near me li** injects the veins directly with a saline solution that makes them cave into a fade from view. This option also helps ease some painful symptoms including aching and swelling.
- If the vein's size is bigger, the **vein doctor near me** may use a device catheter to heat and collapse the diseased veins or he/she can employ vein stripping. Both procedures involve a small incision. In clear words, the professional makes a small incision in the skin to insert and heat a catheter that damages veins. After that, the treated area is closed. With vein stripping, the entire damage part of the veins is removed through the incision.
- Patients who have advanced varicose veins may notice leg ulcers requiring more extensive surgery. [Vein doctor near me Jericho](#) uses the endoscopic method to extract damaged veins, they put a tiny camera inside the vein through an incision. The surgeon removes the diseased veins after locating the affected veins actual position.

If you have varicose veins, talk to your doctor regarding the treatment options asking most suited for your situation.